

Gendered narratives shaping whole-class discussions: Who is invited to present which kinds of solutions?

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In problem-based lessons, teachers invite students to present their ideas to the class. If multiple students arrive at a solution that the teacher wishes be shared, whom do teachers select to present a particular solution and why? Across provided categories of higher-achieving and lower-achieving girls and boys, teacher participants selected boys and girls roughly evenly. However, participants more often indicated intent to invite a lower-achieving girl to present a direct-model solution. On the other hand, participants more often indicated intent to invite a higher-achieving boy to present a more mathematically sophisticated solution. Written justifications for these intentions reveal gendered storylines about mathematics and illustrate an additional way those storylines shape classroom instruction.

Introduction

Problem-based lesson formats often begin with the posing of a mathematical task, allot time for problem-solving, and culminate in a teacher-facilitated whole-class discussion in which specific students are invited to present their work (e.g., Shimizu, 1999; Stein et al., 2008). Inviting students to present mathematical work to their peers encourages the sharing and evaluation of ideas, facilitates an emphasis on reasoning, and distributes both mathematical agency and authority (Gresalfi & Cobb, 2006). In general, when a teacher prompts a student to present ideas to the whole class, this is a public invitation to take a position, ostensibly of a noteworthy mathematical idea. Thus, students' participation in a whole-class discussion is a way of taking up and enacting status-oriented positions a site where social negotiation of "whom we become (in relation to mathematics or otherwise)" and "what we do in the moment (our being)" in classrooms occurs (Black & Radovic, 2018, p. 270).

Social understandings of prompting a student to present ideas to the whole class likely depend on classroom norms (Cobb et al., 2009). In some classrooms, inviting a student to present their ideas might signal the teacher's public assignment of competence (Cohen & Lotan, 1997). In other instances, inviting a student to present a less sophisticated

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mathematical idea (or error) might signal other, less desirable positions. If multiple students arrive at a specific solution that the teacher wishes be shared, whom do teachers select to present a particular solution and why? In particular, we focus on teachers' considerations related to how teachers perceive the intersection of mathematics ability with gender.

Theoretical framework

We acknowledge our problematic reproduction of inaccurate binary notions of gender. Our view of gender is, instead, as socially constructed and performative, rather than as a biological or fixed state of being. Our analysis refers to a context in Israel in which teachers' predominant social understanding of gender in schools is as binary and fixed. Although gender-based differences in school mathematics achievement have narrowed over time, differences in self-concept in mathematics persist, around the world (Sax et al., 2015). We interpret the tendency of girls toward lower self-concept in mathematics as an outcome of social systems that position mathematics as masculine and reinforce boys as better suited for it, rather than evidence of deficiencies innate to girls (Mendick, 2005). All people participate in these social systems, and classrooms are sites in which gender inequalities are re/produced, with parents and teachers playing special roles (Mendick, 2005).

Self-concept in mathematics, or how people see themselves relative to mathematics, is shaped in part by gendered narratives that circulate, are told and retold, and get re/enacted in social interactions in classrooms (Nasir & Shah, 2011). Some are dominant narratives and reinforce social hierarchies. For example, a dominant narrative is that success of high-achieving girls in mathematics is a product of their diligence, whereas boys' success is a product of "bold" problem-solving (Lubienski et al., 2021). A second, related narrative is that mathematical ability is innate, more often among boys (Mendick, 2005). These are but two examples of interrelated narratives that comprise unequal binary oppositions -- like objective/subjective, analytic/emotional, certain/fleeting, innately able/ hard-working, confident/lacking confidence-- wherein one in every pair is more valued *and* associated with masculinity (Mendick, 2005). Although literature in our field often frames these narratives instead as individually-held beliefs, we agree with Parks (2010) and others who problematize that such a framing then implies interventions to change individuals' beliefs rather than a need for broader counternarratives that can challenge those dominant ones.

Related research

Recommendations from teacher education literature

We identified in teacher education literature (TEL) five principles that can guide teachers in how to select and sequence ideas to share. First is "to build a mathematically coherent storyline" (Smith & Stein, 2011, p. 44), in alignment with the lesson's goals. That is, sets (and sequences) of solutions generate *mathematical storylines* by drawing attention to specific mathematical connections. Selecting a sequence of solutions depends on which storyline better aligns with the lesson's mathematical goals. A second principle is around making

mathematics accessible. TEL describes *attending to accessibility* in terms of progressions increasing from concrete to abstract, specific to general, brute force to efficient, or common to unique (Shimizu, 1999; Smith & Stein, 2011). TEL recommends that teachers select and sequence solutions along one of these dimensions and sequence them in an increasing progression (Smith & Stein, 2011).

A third principle privileges, instead, variety in terms of the representations used (numerical, graphical, figurate, formulaic, etc), problem-solving heuristic engaged (solve a smaller problem, work backwards, look for patterns, etc.), or even solutions that produce different results (Stein et al., 2008). A *diverse set of solutions* could be seen to support the contrasting of solutions towards arriving at consensus around which solution is most reasonable or most efficient (Inoue, 2011). Variety would suggest more opportunities for finding more connections across diverse approaches (Larsson & Ryve, 2011). Furthermore, prioritizing or highlighting a diverse set of solutions could be seen to promote values of democratic society in supporting participation around rational, collaborative reasoning. A fourth principle addresses *strategic inclusion of errors*. Engaging errors can deepen mathematical understanding by clarifying the problem situation and normalizes error-making as a natural and inevitable part of doing mathematics (Brodie, 2014). An erroneous solution could resolve misunderstandings, to then enable “work on developing more successful ways of tackling the problem” (Stein et al., 2008, p. 329).

Finally, a fifth principle is around *social considerations* of whom to select as *authors* of solutions to present their ideas. Smith & Stein (2011) suggest that teachers distribute opportunities to present ideas equally, to equally distribute opportunities to “demonstrate their competence and to gain confidence in their abilities (p. 49). Some refer to strategic selection of shy students, or those who have experienced less success in mathematics (Inoue et al., 2019). Groth (2015) cautions that inviting a student to present a “less developed idea” might backfire and ultimately dissuade them from further participation (pp. 14–15).

The principles overlap in various ways. For example, including a particular error might be part of an intended mathematical storyline, a way to scaffold thinking, or a way to position a particular student as having erred. Similarly, a particular diverse set of solutions might also tell an associated mathematical story. However, these five principles demand negotiation, and in many cases, commitments to one principle over another likely guide teachers’ in-the-moment decision-making. Alongside recommendations from TEL is research literature that examines teachers’ practices, in terms of how they negotiate this broader set of principles.

Classroom-based research

Recommendations in TEL and their interpretations by teachers are often divergent; in this case, around teachers’ alternate understandings of the nature and role of classroom discussions (Kosko et al., 2014). Research among teachers, in both U.S. and Australia, for example, shows a foremost emphasis on accessibility considerations (Livy et al., 2017; Meikle, 2014; Tyminski et al., 2014). Most participants of these three studies (pre-service teachers)

indicated that they would sequence presentation of solutions in a progressive order, beginning with what they considered the weakest (incorrect, most incomplete, or direct model) and then progress to what they viewed as the strongest (correct, complete, abstract). In all three studies, participants justified their choice of these progressions in terms of an assumption that such progressions best support students who are struggling. Hewitt (2020) found that in-service elementary teachers attend to accessibility, in terms of the potential of a particular strategy to support engagement. In addition, Hewitt found that teachers attend regularly to mathematical as well as social considerations, paying attention to attending to unequal patterns of participation.

We seek to add to this research by posing the following research question: *With respect to students labelled as lower and higher-achieving girls and boys, whom do teachers select to present which kind of solution and why?*

Research Context

We conducted this study in northern Israel, a context characterized by diversity and straddling a rural/urban divide. Forty-two Israeli teachers participated, in the context of a university-based course; most (38) identify as women and most (37) identify as Palestinian/Arab-Israelis (P/AI). P/AI, unlike those in the West Bank and Gaza, hold citizenship, form nearly one-quarter of Israel's citizenry, and are a slight population-majority in Israel's north. This socially-constructed category encompasses a diversity with ethnic, geographical, linguistic, political, socioeconomic, and religious dimensions. P/AI women, like all women, contend with local patriarchal systems, as well as broader, structural marginalization of women in Israeli society (Yiftachel, 2009). Nevertheless, among P/AIs, girls tend to outperform boys on state and international mathematics tests, at elementary and secondary levels (Rapp, 2015), reversing trends among Israel's majority. Interviews with P/AI women mathematics teachers reveal narratives that girls' excellence and achievement in school mathematics is a result of girls' diligence and understood to be socially valuable (Rubel & Ehrenfeld, 2020; Sabbah & Heyd-Metzuyanin, 2020). Socioeconomic value of this success is tempered, however, by a prevalent routing to teacher education, rather than STEM fields, perpetuated within communities and by majority institutional arrangements (Agbaria & Pinson, 2013).

Methods

We posed this version of the Handshake Problem:

There were 9 players at the first basketball practice of the season. The coach told the players to introduce themselves by shaking hands with one another. Assuming that every player shook hands exactly one time with every other player, how many handshakes occurred?

We provided participants with eight solutions (Figure 1) and prompted them to interpret the mathematical thinking underlying each. We draw attention here (because of their dominance in the results) to solution H, an organized direct-model, and C, one of two

inductive approaches but with a geometric representation. We asked participants to consider a hypothetical upper-track 7th grade class of 32 students and that each solution was produced by four students: higher-achieving/lower-achieving girl or boy. We asked participants to indicate a) which three solutions they would choose to be presented to the class, b) in what sequence, and for each designated solution, c) which student they would choose to present each from among the four categories and why.

A (Additive, no answer). The first player shakes hands with the other eight players. The second shakes seven players' hands, and so on. The number of handshakes decreases in 1 for every other player, until the eight player, who has only one hand to shake. The ninth player does not have any hand to shake. $8 + 7 + \dots + 1$

B (Inductive, tabular, correct answer). In case of 2 players there is one handshake. In case of 3 players there are three handshakes. In case of 4 players there are six handshakes. So I think that $2 + 1 = 3$ is the next result of the number of handshakes (for 3 players). Then $3 + 3 = 6$ is the subsequent number of handshakes (for 4 players). My rule is 'the next number of handshakes = number of players + number of handshakes'.

Number of players	Number of handshakes
2	1
3	3
4	6
5	10
6	15
7	21
8	28
9	36

The answer is 36 handshakes

C (Inductive, geometric, no answer).

3 players – 3 handshakes
 4 players – 6 handshakes
 5 players – 10 handshakes

D (Multiplicative, error). I multiplied 8 in 9 and got 72 handshakes.

E (Additive, correct answer).

$\frac{1}{2} \cdot 9 = 36$

F (Multiplicative, story, correct answer). Every player shakes the hands of the other players – $9 \cdot 8 = 72$. But only half of it, because each handshake involves two players. So the answer is 36 handshakes.

G (Multiplicative, error). $9 \cdot 9 = 81$

H (Direct model, no answer).

(8 handshakes)	1-2	1-3	1-4	1-5	1-6	1-7	1-8	1-9
(7 handshakes)	2-3	2-4	2-5	2-6	2-7	2-8	2-9	
(6 handshakes)	3-4	3-5	3-6	3-7	3-8	3-9		
(5 handshakes)	4-5	4-6	4-7	4-8	4-9			
(4 handshakes)	5-6	5-7	5-8	5-9				
(3 handshakes)	6-7	6-8	6-9					
(2 handshakes)	7-8	7-9						
(1 handshake)	8-9							

Figure 1: Provided Solutions

Analysis

We tabulated the selections, according to position (Table 1) and the assignment of each solution by gender and mathematics achievement (Table 2). We compiled the written justifications for each solution and analyzed those justifications using qualitative thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). We coded a justification as including a gendered narrative if it included statements with girls/boys as the subject of the sentence, e.g., “girls are more creative than boys” (P23) or “boys usually find outstanding solutions more than girls do” (P2). We grouped similar narratives into categories. We identified statements that elaborated the teacher’s sense of the potential impact of inviting a particular student to present an idea, for that student or others and again, grouped similar statements into categories. We repeated the coding process in multiple iterations and resolved disagreements through discussion.

Results

Participants frequently chose C, H, or one of the errors (D or G) (Table 1). Those who selected H, assigned it to first or second position, explaining that it is the most accessible, comprehensive, and confirms the correct answer. Those who chose C assigned it nearly always as the last in the sequence, explaining that it is “non-routine” and “creative.” Participants commonly cited accessibility considerations in justifying such a sequencing, beginning with the direct model or an error and ending with an inductive solution translated into geometric terms. Overall, participants selected boys or girls roughly evenly overall (Table 2). Two gender-related patterns are evident: Participants commonly invited 1) a lower-achieving girl to present H and 2) a higher-achieving boy to present C.

Solution	1st choice	2nd choice	3rd choice	Total
A Additive	2	9	0	11 (26%)
B Inductive, Tabular	0	2	4	6 (14%)
C Inductive, Geometric	0	4	30	34 (81%)
D or G Errors	21	8	0	29 (69%)
E Multiplicative, Exp.	1	3	1	5 (12%)
F Multiplicative, story	2	6	1	9 (21%)
H Direct model	16	10	6	32 (76%)

Table 1: Selection of Solutions in Sequence

Of the 32 who chose Solution H, 23 chose a girl, and nearly always (19, 59%) a lower-achieving girl. Participants indicated a range of narratives: several about girls’ mathematical weaknesses (e.g., “Girls usually choose the long and safe way” P27) and several about girls’ presentation skills (e.g., “She will be able to simplify the explanation in friendly terms” P25). However, the most frequently repeated narrative (by 16 participants) addressed an intended outcome, that inviting a lower-achieving girl would attend to the girl’s lack of self-confidence, self-concept, and rate of participation. As an example, P23 said, “it is known that girls generally have low self-confidence, I wanted to give her support and for her to experience success, especially since this is clear and correct, and in addition, this can encourage the rest of the girls with low self-confidence.”

In contrast, of the 34 who chose C, 22 indicated that they would invite a boy to present it, nearly always (17) a higher-achieving boy. This time, the narratives were around boys’ mathematical reasoning strengths or communication skills. Participants attributed characteristics to these boys such as “outstanding,” “creative,” and “special”. For example, P26 explained that “on the basis of experience, boys like busy-work less than girls, and mostly try to find other ways to solve a problem. In addition, boys have better spatial abilities than girls, so this solution is better suited to a boy.” In contrast to solution H, few (3) told narratives about the potential contribution of inviting a higher-achieving boy to present C,

for the student or for other class members. When, on the other hand, participants assigned solution C to higher-achieving girls (this occurred much less often), they tended, again, to explain this as an opportunity to remedy those girls' lack of self-confidence. For example, P8 explained "Girls don't have self-confidence, and are shy, so I chose a girl because boys have self-confidence, to go to the board and to talk in front of the class."

	B-Low	G-Low	B- or G-Low	B-High	G-High	B- or G-High	Total n (%)
A Additive	4	6	1	0	0	0	11 (26%)
B Inductive, Tabular	1	0	0	2	3	0	6 (14%)
C Inductive, Geometric	5	2	0	17	6	4	34 (81%)
D or G Errors	5	3	1	10	7	3	29 (69%)
E Multiplicative, Exp.	3	0	0	2	0	0	5 (12%)
F Multiplicative, story	2	1	1	1	4	0	9 (21%)
H Direct model	4	19	2.5*	2	4	0.5*	32 (76%)
Total	24	31	5.5	34	24	7.5	126

*Value of 0.5 resulted from one participant indicating all 4 student categories

Table 2: Assignment of selected solutions by gender and math status

Discussion

Our results suggest that social considerations play a significant role in teachers' decision-making about whom to invite to present which kind of solution for a whole-class discussion. Many indicated a preference for a direct model solution and that they would invite a lower-achieving girl to present it. In nearly all cases, they designated direct-model H as first or second to be presented. If there is a classroom norm around supporting accessibility by always beginning with the easiest example or least sophisticated solution, as prior studies indicate (Livy et al., 2017; Meikle, 2014), then inviting a lower-achieving girl to present first or early on signals to the class (and to the girl herself) that her solution holds a low value. Inviting a lower-achieving girl to present her mathematical ideas as a way to attend to her perceived low self-confidence would likely undermine that intention. Instead, this arrangement likely reinforces any positions of low self-confidence and might ultimately dissuade them from further participation.

With respect to the more sophisticated solution C, most participants chose this to be included and more often indicated that they would invite a higher-achieving boy to present C. Here, too, the sequencing is significant, as in most cases, participants sequenced C to be last. Again, if there is a classroom norm around the sequencing of examples or ideas, as the prior research indicates, then being invited to present later in the sequence likely signals the value of this solution to the class, as most sophisticated. These findings support (and are

supported by) the dominant narrative that boys' excellence in mathematics is a function of their mathematical talent.

Although this was not a study aimed to study gender-bias specifically among P/AI teachers, because nearly all of the participants identify as P/AI, we add an interpretation of these results with respect to this particular socio-political context. Prior research locates a trend that girls among P/AI people outperform boys in school mathematics and speculates underlying contributing factors, from a lack of school-based opportunities in Israel's Arab school sector other than mathematics, an agentic response by P/AI girls and women for self-realization or to challenge underestimation of their capabilities (Rubel & Ehrenfeld, 2020). This study's results suggest a preliminary picture of how classroom socialization processes might reinforce the status quo. These processes likely contribute to how, on the one hand, higher-achieving P/AI girls mostly pursue feminized (and lower paying) professions and, on the other hand, lower-achieving P/AI girls struggle to access higher education or secure employment (see Haj-Yahya et al., 2018).

Two groups of students figure significantly less prominently in these results: higher-achieving girls and lower-achieving boys. The tendency here of public positioning of higher-achieving boys as exceptional (more often than higher-achieving girls) likely compounds the narrative that girls succeed because of diligence rather than brilliance. This is consequential in the local context: although P/AI girls tend to out-participate and out-score boys in K-12 mathematics, they largely continue towards teacher education rather than STEM disciplines or careers. At the same time, although participants indicate that they view invitations to a student to present an idea on the public floor as a resource for confidence-building, their assignments suggested their view of this resource as predominantly for lower-achieving girls. We are curious to further explore narratives about lower-achieving boys to interpret why they figure less often in these results.

An important limitation to this study is that it is oriented around a single mathematics task. We did not specify to participants a learning goal for the hypothetical lesson or imagined whole-class discussion. In addition, we have flattened social diversity into two social constructs (perceived gender and ability) and separated those into artificial binary distinctions. These variables do not operate in binary terms and intersect with other social markers, such as race, language status, physical appearance, social popularity, and more. Nevertheless, these results illuminate how circulating dominant narratives about gender and mathematics shape teachers' decision-making regarding whom to invite to present which kind of solution on the classroom's public floor. In the life of a classroom, consequences of those decisions likely include the reinforcing of those dominant narratives and the gendered hierarchies they represent.

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